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Subject: Living labs

[CAUTION: EXTERNAL EMAIL]

Dear DEC Colleagues,

As part of the ongoing development of the ENRA Research Strategy 2027–2032, we are seeking examples of living labs/farm demonstrator initiatives that exemplify the co-creation of land management solutions through collaborative, place-based research. Living Labs are being recognised as a core delivery mechanism for the next research cycle.

They are expected to play a central role in supporting transformative land use and better land management practices, helping to deliver on multiple national goals including those in the Vision for Agriculture, the Climate Change Plan, the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy, and the Just Transition and Good Food Nation acts.

We are therefore inviting case studies from the current and past Research Portfolios to include within the 2027-32 ENRA Research Strategy that:

- Illustrate how scientific research has been jointly developed with practitioners (e.g. farmers, crofters, land managers, regulators, communities)
- Demonstrate how such co-development has led to practical changes in land use and management, delivering outcomes supporting SG objectives (see above)
- Showcase early-stage or mature Living Lab models in Scotland (e.g. upland/peatland restoration, nutrient efficiency, circular bioeconomy, agroforestry, or breeding innovation) – graphics, photos welcome

Please submit one or two short case studies (1 page of text maximum for each) by **Friday 20 June**, highlighting the above.

We also welcome your thoughts on the co-development process and ideas for scaling or replicating Living Labs across Scotland.

Thank you in advance for your contributions and collaboration.

Best regards,

Many thanks,

Natalie White
Business and Scientific Support Officer
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